

SOCIAL COMMUNICATION STUDIES

DIGITALIZATION OF SERVICES: THE IMPACT ON TOURISM SECTOR IN ALBANIA

Ermelinda S.,

*PhD. Candidate, South East European University,
Faculty of Contemporary Social Science, Tetovo-Macedonia*

Françeska Sh.,

*Student, Department of Economy and Rural Development Policies,
Agricultural University of Tirana, Tirana Albania*

Sajmir R.

*Student, Department of Economy and Rural Development Policies,
Agricultural University of Tirana, Tirana Albania*

Abstract

At a time when technological innovations and artificial intelligence have spread in every field of life and are facilitating the provision of many services, tourism has also become subject of these developments. However, the digitalization of the tourist services sector in Albania is low and there are a number of problems, which have been identified in the National Strategy for the Sustainable Development of Tourism 2019-2023, drawn up by the Ministry of Tourism and Environment of the Republic of Albania. The purpose of this study is to assess the degree of spread and impact of digitalization of services in the public and private spheres of tourism, and more specifically in travel agencies and tour operators in Albania. The main instrument used to collect quantitative data was a questionnaire designed with Google Forms, which was distributed to travel agencies and tour operators and was completed in person with representatives of these businesses. After the research work, it was concluded that facing foreign competitors, already digitalized, while Albania gradually enters a global tourist market, could bring out of operation most of the tour operators and travel agencies, bringing a collapse in the way this sector has traditionally developed. Recommendations for better management of the current situation would include the engagement of policy makers in information campaigns with businesses, regarding the advantages of digitalization in competition, productivity and sustainable development.

Keywords: digitalization, travel agencies, tour operators, digital tourism, e-Albania.

1. Introduction:

The world as we know it is changing rapidly and technology is the incentive for the betterment of the sector of services, particularly in the tourism industry. Innovations in receiving tourist services online are removing geographical barriers between tourists and host countries, creating opportunities to make any reservation or payment through the screen of a digital device. Findings from American Express Travel's "Global Travel Trends 2023" report suggests that Gen Z (people born 1997-2012) and Millennials (people born 1981-1996) are more likely to travel in 2023 compared to every other generation (54% and 43% versus an average of 41%), with their behaviors expected to make a difference in the travel sector. In Albania, according to the 2021 report "Tourism in Figures" by the Institute of Statistics INSTAT, it is noted that 57.6% of foreign tourists were of this age group and the numbers are increasing. Although Albania is currently a tourist attraction popular with Europeans, this does not ensure the continuation of the upward trends for years, especially as digitalization is becoming a crucial part of the consumer experience. Since technology is advancing rapidly, nowadays the only "weapon" that agencies have is a good marketing and that it can be achieved by all individuals is only through technology. Currently, the document of the National Strategy for Tourism, 2019 - 2023 lists digitization and the limited use of information technology in tourism among the weak points to be addressed in the next 4 years. However, this remains a complex sector affected by negative phenomenon

such as the high informality of the sector and the high use of cash in payments for this service. Increasingly, information technology is becoming a key factor in the development of tourism in Albania. In recent years, Albania has had a significant increase in the number of tourists from abroad, mainly from European countries. Tour operators are making extensive use of information technology for the promotion of tourist destinations, the interaction between tour operators, and the continuous and sustainable increase in the number of tourists. In this context, they have created data banks and exchange information through different ways such as the Internet and different applications. Public institutions have mainly been content with drafting policies for the development of tourism and action plans in support of the tourist season. For all of the above, this study aims to reflect in detail the digital development of the public and private tourism sector in Albania, specifically of travel agencies and tour operators, analysis that comes after the identification of poor digitalization as a problem highlighted by the Ministry of Tourism of Albania. The description of digital public services offered by e-Albania for businesses in the field of tourism, the analysis of the indicators of digitalization in the private sector and the identification of difficulties and opportunities in the inclusion of digitalization in the tourism sector are some of the objectives of this study.

1.2 Statement of the Problem

In recent years, the global shift towards digitalization has significantly transformed various industries, including the tourism sector. In the context of Albania,

a country with a growing tourism industry, the integration of digital technologies into service delivery has become increasingly prominent. However, the implications and challenges posed by the digitalization of services in the Albanian tourism sector remain underexplored. This research aims to address the gap in understanding the specific impact, opportunities, and challenges associated with the digital transformation of tourism services in Albania. By investigating the current state of digitalization, identifying key trends, and evaluating the perceptions of stakeholders, this study seeks to provide valuable insights into how digital technologies are influencing the tourism landscape in Albania and to propose strategic recommendations for the sustainable advancement of the industry. In conclusion, it is a fact that recently, we have been hearing a lot of talk about digitization in tourism. Digitalization plays an important role in the tourism sector and has major impacts on the way how the travelers plan, book and experience their trips. Since 2021 in Albania every public service has been digitized through the e-Albania platform, this innovation has brought benefits and achievements in the tourism sector as well, a field that needs to be studied.

1.3 Purpose and objectives of the study

This paper aims to determine the impact of the development of digitization mainly on the travel agencies and tour operators in Tirana, including the current development and the capacity of digitalization of the tourism sector, analysis that comes after the identification of poor digitalization as a problem highlighted by the Ministry of Tourism of Albania, without excluding the relationship that the latter creates in customer service and the facilities it offers both for agencies and for consumers.

Objectives:

- The role of digitization in tourism agencies
- The description of digital public services offered by e-Albania for businesses in the field of tourism
- The analysis of the indicators of digitalization in the private sector
- The identification of difficulties and opportunities in the inclusion of digitalization in the tourism sector; are some of the objectives of this study.

Hypothesis:

The hypothesis raised is that the current operating travel agencies and tour operators is quite indifferent to digitalization and for this reason, in a competitive market like that of tourism, this proves a pessimistic perspective for the country's tourism development, especially when the two most travel-prone age groups in the world are precisely those who grew up in the era of technological developments.

2. Methodology:

2.1 Description of the research design

The research method used in the study is the quantitative method of data collection, analysis and interpretation. Quantitative method was used, as it provides an understanding of the issue addressed, including a considerable number of subjects in a short time. The quantitative research in the study is built on the basis of the case study strategy. The case that is the basis of the research, are tourist agencies that operate in the market

located in the area of Tirana and offer services and sell tourist packages from other operators. Quantitative research involves the collection, analysis, and interpretation of data to gain insight into a particular phenomenon that the authors are interested in. A structured questionnaire was used as the main instrument to collect the quantitative data of the study.

2.2 Study population and the sample

The group of subjects selected for this study consists of travel agencies and tourist operators operating in Tirana. The study is based on a sample of 20 travel agencies and 5 tour operators. The selection of the subjects was carried out in such a way that they met the conditions set pre-practically by the researchers.

Sampling

The sample of this study consists of travel agencies and tourist operators that exercise their activity in Tirana. The agencies selected to be part of the research were randomly selected in different areas in Tirana.

2.3 Data collection

The selection of the method for collecting the data of the study has been one of the main issues throughout the development of the study. For data collection, possible methods were browsed and researched, always taking into consideration the field and topic of the study, after browsing it was decided as the most appropriate, that in this study for data collection to use the structured questionnaire. Important in using this method was the good presentation of the purpose, objectives and hypotheses. This method allows the researcher to be flexible and in turn allows the interviewee to choose a time that suits them best for filling out the form. The data collection process took a period of 3 weeks. Data collection as mentioned above was done using the face-to-face questionnaire in the premises of the subjects selected in the study. Specifically, the completion of the questionnaire was done in a period of 3 weeks, from the end of November to the beginning of December 2023. Completing the questionnaire required a completion time of 10-15 minutes at most.

2.4 Design of research instruments

The scientific research involved restructuring and analyzing information based on the insight obtained from a survey divided into four sections. Each section had the corresponding questions, in total 30 questions, where there were defined alternatives as well as some of them determined with the Likert scale. Participants could choose only one of the defined alternatives. One of the primary methods employed to construct this survey involved the use of close-ended questions. A thorough review of the survey questions was conducted in face-to-face sessions with representatives from tourist agencies. The time used to gather the information granted was a month, starting on the end of November 2023 until December 2023 and the work analysis became more detailed with the assistance of graphics, which showcased the core information. The measurement of the degree of digitalization of tourist agencies and tour operators in this study was done through a set of indicators. These indicators include the use of technological devices in the workplace and a digital database, a good and collaborative work online, presence

on social networks the use of common office software, etc. The sampling for this study comprises tourist agencies operating in Tirana, supported by a sample of 20 tourist agencies and 5 tour operators. In the second phase, the research was predominantly focused on discussions and literature review, which provided a clear framework for exploration and facilitating in-depth discussions. A crucial resource was the data research conducted by INSTAT, providing essential information on the digitalization within the tourism sector. While the data analysis lasted about 5 days. The analysis of the data was realized with Google Forms, through which the results for each question defined in the questionnaire were published. During the collection and analysis of the data, despite the fact that the participation was completely voluntary, the main principles of ethics were followed in the study, where all subjects participating in the study gave their consent to become part of the study, after being informed on the purpose, objectives and reasons for obtaining this information and how their data would be used. The confidentiality of the subjects involved in the study has been preserved.

3. Analysis and Data

The group of subjects selected for this study consists of travel agencies and tourist operators operating in Tirana. The study is based on a sample of 20 travel agencies and 5 tour operators. The selection of the subjects was carried out in such a way that they met the conditions set pre-practically by the researchers.

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Figure 1. How long has the subject been active for?

Source: Author's processing

In the context of the graph in the Figure 1., it is evident that every surveyed travel agency and tour operator has maintained their operations for a minimum duration of one year, with none of them reporting an operational history of less than one year. The distribution of these entities reveals that 15% of them have been active for a duration spanning 1-2 years, 10% for 3-5 years, and a majority of 75% for more than 5 years.

Figure 2. What are the factor hindering the digitalization of the business?

Source: Author's processing

According to the graph in the Figure 2. it's obvious: The lack of funds for investing in the digitalization of the business 15%. - The absence of current plans for the digitalization process 25%. - The lack of a qualified and a digitally skilled staff 25%. - All of the above 30%. -

Figure 3. How important is digitalization to the business?"

Source: Author's processing

What it is describe in the Figure 3, it's that 50% of the subject in the study consider very important the digitalization in their business, and in the same time 50% of them consider important the digitalization aspect.

Figure 4. What is your strategy for the future of your business?

Source: Author's processing

The largest percentage 70%, in the answers of respondents is the partial digital transformation of some work processes, but the majority of activities are still carried out physically 25% affirm the importance of the complete digital transformation of the business, leading to a 100% online shift, like future strategy. Only 5% emphasize like strategy the continuity of the traditional way of doing business.-

Figure 5. Have you taken any steps toward digitalizing the work process?

Source: Author's processing

Since digitization is a phenomenon that has been developing a lot lately in our country, all the participants have thought about it 20% and 65% are planning to further develop the aspects of digitization.

Figure 6. Do you believe that the digitalization of the tourism sector poses a threat to your operations as a travel agency or tour operator?

Source: Author's processing

According to the graph in Figure 6, 15% agree. The business would never manage to transform entirely in the digital aspect. - 60% Disagree, on the contrary, the business would manage to adapt to new trends and benefit from them. - and 25% don't think that there would be a noticeable impact. -

4. Results and Discussion:

The results revealed a notable increase in the adoption of digital services across the industry. Online booking platforms, mobile applications, and virtual tours have become prevalent tools for both tourists and service providers. According to the travel agencies and tour operators, tourists expressed a positive shift in their overall experience due to digital advancements. The convenience of online bookings, real-time information access, and personalized recommendations were highlighted as significant contributors to enhanced satisfaction levels. As the results of the study, service providers, on the other hand, acknowledged the efficiency gains brought about by digitalization. Improved operational processes, better resource management, and increased visibility in the online marketplace were identified as key benefits. However, challenges such as cybersecurity concerns and the need for continuous staff training were also recognized. In the other hand, the discussion section delves into the interpretation and implications of the results, providing a deeper understanding of the impact of digitalization on the tourism sector in Albania. The positive feedback from tourists indicates a growing demand for digitally facilitated services. It is evident that tourists now expect seamless digital experiences, from pre-trip planning to on-site activities. This shift necessitates a continuous commitment from the tourism industry to invest in and adapt to evolving digital trends. Also, service providers benefit significantly from the integration of digital tools. The streamlining of operations and the ability to reach a broader audience contribute to the overall growth and competitiveness of businesses within the sector. The discussion emphasizes the importance of service providers staying attuned to emerging technologies and consumer preferences. About the challenges and areas for improvement the discussion of the studies explores potential solutions and highlights the need for collaborative efforts between the public and private sectors to address these challenges effectively.

In conclusion, the study provides a comprehensive understanding of the impact of digitalization on the

tourism sector in Albania. The positive outcomes and challenges identified lay the groundwork for future strategies and initiatives aimed at fostering a digitally resilient and visitor-friendly tourism industry.

5. Conclusions:

- This research highlighted the underdeveloped way in which technology is incorporated into the daily work of economic entities in the field of tourism.

- The data analysis shows that 99% of Travel Agencies and Tour Operators are endowed with practical technological devices, like PC, Scanner, Printer.

- All the subjects in the study have created a digital database, example Google Sheets, that entails information about their clients, also they have the capability to extend their working hours to locations beyond their offices.

- According to the results, 99% of Travel Agencies and Tour Operators use social media platforms as integral channels for marketing and communicating.

- A number of travel agencies and tour operators use an online booking system with a wide B2B database, becoming distributors of the largest travel companies, while the rest operates through contracts with foreign agencies that bring tourists to Albania.

- The majority of the bookings of tour or holiday packages by the Albanian citizens are made at the offices or through phone calls and text messages. Rarely is the entire reservation and payment made by digital means, specially 65% of Travel Agencies and Tour Operators surveyed, accept payment made possible with credit cards, which leaves 35% incapable of accepting this method of payment

- Most of the travel agencies and tour operators have access and use the government's websites frequently.

- 45% of the agencies affirm that the digital transformation of the business will facilitate the distribution and sale of their products and services. On the other hand, 35% of the subjects describe the digital transformation of the business will make it more efficient and profitable by reducing costs and increasing revenues.

- Through digitalization, a sufficiently advanced network of communication and information transmission has been created, so that some use chatbots for communication with customers.

6. Recommendations

- The role of the government in fostering a conducive digital environment is discussed. The study suggests that policymakers should consider creating supportive frameworks, investing in digital infrastructure, and promoting digital literacy to ensure a sustainable and inclusive digital transformation.
- Technology is always changing greatly, so agencies must be alert to changes and staff training to be in the market and to ensure a higher profit.
- In the future, travel agencies and tourist operators should use more online payments instead of cash, creating flexibility and convenience for all customers everywhere.
- Evaluate the level of training and skill development provided to employees regarding digital tools and technologies. This is crucial for ensuring that the workforce is equipped to leverage digital resources effectively.
- Studies should be developed in this sector and educational practices for tourism should be increased, as it is one of the areas that brings a lot of profits to the country's economy, family economy as well as foreign investments.
- Explore the adoption of emerging technologies such as artificial intelligence, chatbots, and virtual/augmented reality in enhancing customer experiences and streamlining operations.

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